

THE IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING TECHNOLOGICAL CULTURE AND TRIZ TECHNOLOGY IN FOSTERING FUTURE TEACHER'S SOCIAL-PROFESSIONAL MOBILITY

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ABSTRACT

This article highlights the importance of technological culture in increasing social and professional mobility of future teachers, as well as the goals and methods of using TRIZ technology in the example of "Integrated Speech Skills".

Introduction. New, effective language-didactic models and methods of training future teachers, improving the level of professional training of future specialists in teaching foreign languages are being applied to the educational process in higher educational institutions of the world. For students who want to learn the language, the task of setting up language teaching courses at the level of communication in higher education institutions has been set as a priority. As a result, opportunities for continuous self-development are intensive and improvement at all stages of one's professional life. The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 "On the new Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" [1], serves to implement the tasks defined in other regulatory legal documents related to this activity.

Important changes taking place in all spheres of social and spiritual life have a unique effect on the state of modern education. It can be seen that the effectiveness of the work of specialists is determined by the level of personal and professional compliance with the specific nature of the professional reality. In this regard, the issue of the specific characteristics of pedagogical conditions to increase the socio-professional mobility of future teachers and their personal development is of particular relevance. The latter is defined as the process and result of the formation of professionally important characteristics of a specialist, which is the system of his values and emotional relationships that affect the effectiveness of professional activity.

Literature analysis and methods

Acquiring technological culture is important for the development of social and professional mobility for future foreign language teachers. Today, the activity of young foreign language teachers is not sufficiently developed. Many university graduates do not always have the opportunity to apply the knowledge gained during the introduction of new alternative pedagogical technologies, to perform professional functions. In addition, they face great

difficulties in adapting the methods of managing the educational process at school. Also, improvement of social and cultural competences of students of G. N. Djuraeva higher educational institutions is relevant today, because more practicing teachers use materials of local studies in foreign language teaching. He emphasized that this is due to the fact that it is gaining importance in the presentation of cultures at the international level. [2; p. 20]

In the 1st-2nd years, we conducted experimental tests on the subject "Integration of speech skills", and within the framework of these subjects, students perfectly learn listening comprehension, speaking, reading and writing skills, and these skills are even easier to learn with modern technologies. There is no doubt about their abilities. In the subject of integration of speech skills, students learn listening comprehension and speaking skills. We effectively used synchronous and asynchronous educational technologies in the process of conducting the subject "Integration of Speech Skills". With new inventions in this technology being made every day, students can learn in or out of the classroom. Learning can be self-paced with the help of various resources available on the Internet, synchronous learning and asynchronous learning. Now students can study online through distance learning programs and virtual classes.

Synchronous learning, as its name means "existing or happening at the same time," refers to the discussion of ideas and information on specific topics with others at the same time. Some examples are people working together online, such as face-to-face discussions, chat rooms or virtual classrooms, live teaching and feedback sessions, Skype chats, etc. As students work in groups, they expand their range of possibilities. They learn a lot of information by listening to the opinions of others on the same topics. It also helps them learn and gather more information, which helps them further their knowledge. In addition, there is a communicative method, the most important advantage of which is that it has many different exercises: role-playing games, dialogues and simulation of real communication are used here. We also used TRIZ (Theory of Inventive Problem Solving) technologies to develop speaking skills. The strategic goal of this pedagogy is the comprehensive development of the student's creative abilities.

Results

In the control phase of the study, 18.8% of students (35 people) could not answer about their mobility ("I don't know" answers of the fifth group). Previously, this figure was 93.8% of students. In this way, the number of respondents decreased by 75% compared to the discovery phase of the experiment. However, all students participating in the experiment (187 people - 100%) are convinced that social and professional mobility is an important quality for a modern teacher (answers of the sixth group). The number of students calculating in this method increased by 27.5% compared to 72.5% obtained during the detection experiment. These facts are undoubtedly positive. Thus, the qualitative analysis of the performed work does not contradict, on the contrary, it confirms the obtained quantitative data.

After conducting a control test on individual components of socio-professional mobility, based on the total score, it was possible to determine that 35 percent of the total number of participants in the experiment (65 people) were able to achieve a high level of development. Development of mobility, 45% of students (84 people) recorded an average level, 10% of students (19 people) remained at a low level.

At the end of the study, the number of students with high mobility increased by 17.5% (33 people) compared to the data at the beginning of the pilot study and shows a double increase. The number of students with low mobility decreased by more than half and reached 10% (19

people) - the difference was 13.7% (26 people). Undoubtedly, the decrease in the average level is due to the transition of some students to a group with a highly developed socio-professional mobility: the initial indicator was 58.8% (110 people), the control indicator was 45% (84).

TRIZ technology is an effective technology for developing analytical and systematic thinking. Recently, more and more teachers are using the project methodology in the process of teaching a foreign language as one of the modern effective creative approaches, which is important for the formation of communicative and speech skills that successfully carry out the main tasks of teaching a foreign language and for students to communicate in a foreign language. The main goal of the project method is to give students the opportunity to learn independently in the process of solving practical tasks or problems that require the integration of knowledge from different disciplines. If we talk about the method of projects as a pedagogical technology, this technology includes a complex of research, research, and problem-solving methods of a creative nature. In the project, the teacher was appointed as a developer, coordinator, expert and consultant.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can mention that, this technology helps to develop students' creative abilities, develops their imagination and interests. During the preparation of projects, the creative and intellectual potential of the student is revealed. The project method teaches how to conduct research, work in a team, hold a discussion, and solve problems. The project method can be used in teaching a foreign language on almost any subject, because the choice of subjects was made taking into account their practical importance for the student.

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